

ON THE GENERALIZATION OF THE FLOOR OF THE SQUARE ROOT SEQUENCE

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Abstract The floor of the square root sequence is the natural sequence, where each number is repeated $2n + 1$ times. In this paper, we use analytic method to study the mean value properties of its generalization, and give an interesting asymptotic formula.

Keywords: the floor of the square root sequence; mean value; asymptotic formula.

§1. Introduction

The floor of the square roots of the natural numbers are:

0, 1, 1, 1, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 4, 4, 4, 4, 4, 4, 4, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 6, 6,
6, 6, 6, 6, 6, 6, 6, 6, 6, 6, 7, 7, 7, 7, 7, 7, 7, 7, 7, 7, 7, 7, 8, \dots

This sequence is the natural sequence, where each number is repeated $2n + 1$ times. In reference [1], Professor F.Smarandache asked us to study the properties of this sequence. We denote the generalization of the sequence as $b(n)$, in which each number is repeated $kn + 1$ times, and express it as $b(n) = [n^{1/k}]$. In reference [2], He Xiaolin and Guo Jinbao studied the mean value of $d(b(n))$, and obtain an asymptotic formula for it. In this paper, as a generalization of [2], we use analytic method to study the mean value properties of $\sigma_\alpha(b(n))$, and give a general asymptotic formula for $\sigma_\alpha(b(n))$. That is, we shall prove the following :

Theorem. For any real number $x > 1$ and integer $n \geq 1$, we have

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \sigma_\alpha(b(n)) = \begin{cases} \frac{k\zeta(\alpha+1)}{\alpha+k} x^{\frac{\alpha+k}{k}} + O(x^{\frac{\beta+k-1}{k}}), & \text{if } \alpha > 0; \\ \frac{1}{k} x \log x + O(x), & \text{if } \alpha = 0; \\ \zeta(2)x + O(x^{\frac{k+\varepsilon-1}{k}}), & \text{if } \alpha = -1; \\ \zeta(1-\alpha)x + O(x^{\frac{\delta+k-1}{k}}), & \text{if } \alpha < 0 \text{ and } \alpha \neq -1 \end{cases}$$

where $\sigma_\alpha(n) = \sum_{d|n} d^\alpha$ be the divisor function, $\zeta(n)$ be the Riemann Zeta function, $\beta = \max\{1, \alpha\}$, $\delta = \max\{0, 1 + \alpha\}$ and $\varepsilon > 0$ be an arbitrary real number.

§2. Proof of the Theorem

In this section, we shall complete the proof of the theorem. Firstly, we need following:

Lemma 1. Let $\alpha > 0$ be a fixed real number. Then for $x > 1$, we have

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \sigma_{\alpha}(n) = \frac{\zeta(\alpha + 1)}{\alpha + 1} x^{\alpha+1} + O(x^{\beta}),$$

and

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \sigma_{-\alpha}(n) = \begin{cases} \zeta(\alpha + 1)x + O(x^{\delta}), & \text{if } \alpha \neq 1; \\ \zeta(2)x + O(\log x), & \text{if } \alpha = 1. \end{cases}$$

where $\beta = \max\{1, \alpha\}$, $\delta = \max\{0, 1 - \alpha\}$, $\zeta(n)$ denotes the Riemann zeta-function.

Proof See reference [3].

Lemma 2. Let n be a positive integer, and $b(n) = [n^{1/k}]$, $d(n)$ be the divisor function, then

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \sigma_0(b(n)) = \sum_{n \leq x} d([n^{1/k}]) = \frac{1}{k} x \log x + O(x).$$

Proof. See reference [2].

Now we use the above Lemmas to complete the proof of Theorem. We separate α into three cases respectively.

Case 1, when $\alpha > 0$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \leq x} \sigma_{\alpha}(b(n)) &= \sum_{n \leq x} \sigma_{\alpha}([n^{1/k}]) \\ &= \sum_{1^k \leq n < 2^k} \sigma_{\alpha}([n^{1/k}]) + \sum_{2^k \leq n < 3^k} \sigma_{\alpha}([n^{1/k}]) + \dots \\ &\quad + \sum_{N^k \leq n < (N+1)^k} \sigma_{\alpha}([n^{1/k}]) + O(N^{\beta}) \\ &= \sum_{j \leq N} \left((j+1)^k - j^k \right) \sigma_{\alpha}(j) + O(N^{\beta}). \end{aligned}$$

Let $A(n) = \sum_{n \leq x} \sigma_{\alpha}(j)$ and $f(j) = \sum_{j \leq N} \left((j+1)^k - j^k \right)$, applying Abel's identity and Lemma 1, we have

$$\begin{aligned} &\sum_{n \leq x} \sigma_{\alpha}(b(n)) \\ &= A(N)f(N) - A(1)f(1) - \int_1^N A(t)f'(t)dt + O(N^{\beta}) \\ &= \frac{k\zeta(\alpha + 1)}{\alpha + 1} N^{\alpha+k} - k(k-1) \int_1^N \frac{\zeta(\alpha + 1)}{\alpha + k} t^{\alpha+k+1} dt \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & +O(N^{\beta+k-1}) \\
 = & \frac{k\zeta(\alpha+1)}{\alpha+k}N^{\alpha+k} + O(N^{\beta+k-1}) \\
 = & \frac{k\zeta(\alpha+1)}{\alpha+k}x^{\frac{\alpha+k}{k}} + O(x^{\frac{\beta+k-1}{k}}).
 \end{aligned}$$

Case 2, when $\alpha = -1$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sum_{n \leq x} \sigma_{-1}(b(n)) &= \sum_{n \leq x} \sigma_{-1}([n^{1/k}]) \\
 &= \sum_{1^k \leq n < 2^k} \sigma_{-1}([n^{1/k}]) + \sum_{2^k \leq n < 3^k} \sigma_{-1}([n^{1/k}]) + \dots \\
 &\quad + \sum_{N^k \leq n < (N+1)^k} \sigma_{-1}([n^{1/k}]) + O(N^\varepsilon) \\
 &= \sum_{j \leq N} ((j+1)^k - j^k) \sigma_{-1}(j) + O(N^\varepsilon).
 \end{aligned}$$

Let $A(n) = \sum_{j \leq N} \sigma_{-1}(j)$ and $f(j) = \sum_{j \leq N} ((j+1)^k - j^k)$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sum_{n \leq x} \sigma_{-1}(b(n)) &= \sum_{n \leq x} \sigma_{-1}[n^{1/k}] \\
 &= A(N)f(N) - A(1)f(1) - \int_1^N A(t)f'(t)dt + O(N^\varepsilon) \\
 &= \zeta(2)N^k + O(N^{k+\varepsilon-1}) \\
 &= \zeta(2)x + O(x^{\frac{k+\varepsilon-1}{k}}),
 \end{aligned}$$

where $\varepsilon > 0$ be an arbitrary real number.

Case 3, when $\alpha < 0$ and $\alpha \neq -1$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sum_{n \leq x} \sigma_\alpha(b(n)) &= \sum_{n \leq x} \sigma_\alpha([n^{1/k}]) \\
 &= \sum_{1^k \leq n < 2^k} \sigma_\alpha([n^{1/k}]) + \sum_{2^k \leq n < 3^k} \sigma_\alpha([n^{1/k}]) + \dots \\
 &\quad + \sum_{N^k \leq n < (N+1)^k} \sigma_\alpha([n^{1/k}]) + O(N^\delta) \\
 &= \sum_{j \leq N} ((j+1)^k - j^k) \sigma_\alpha(j) + O(N^\delta).
 \end{aligned}$$

Let $A(n) = \sum_{j \leq N} \sigma_\alpha(j)$ and $f(j) = \sum_{j \leq N} ((j+1)^k - j^k)$, we have

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \sigma_\alpha(b(n)) = \sum_{n \leq x} \sigma_\alpha([n^{1/k}])$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= A(N)f(N) - A(1)f(1) - \int_1^N A(t)f'(t)dt + O(N^\delta) \\
&= k\zeta(1-\alpha)N^k + O(N^{k+\delta-1}) - (k-1)\zeta(1-\alpha)N^k \\
&= \zeta(1-\alpha)N^k + O(N^{k+\delta-1}) \\
&= \zeta(1-\alpha)x + O(x^{\frac{\delta+k-1}{k}}).
\end{aligned}$$

Combining the above result, we have

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \sigma_\alpha(b(n)) = \begin{cases} \frac{k\zeta(\alpha+1)}{\alpha+k} x^{\frac{\alpha+k}{k}} + O(x^{\frac{\beta+k-1}{k}}), & \text{if } \alpha > 0; \\ \frac{1}{k} x \log x + O(x), & \text{if } \alpha = 0; \\ \zeta(2)x + O(x^{\frac{k+\varepsilon-1}{k}}), & \text{if } \alpha = -1; \\ \zeta(1-\alpha)x + O(x^{\frac{\delta+k-1}{k}}), & \text{if } \alpha < 0 \text{ and } \alpha \neq -1 \end{cases}$$

This completes the proof of Theorem.

References

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